

TUMORS IMPORTANCE OF MRI IN THE DIAGNOSIS OF CARDIAC

Nishonova Yulduzkhon Khatamovna
Dalikusiev Sardorbek Shukhratovich

Tashkent State Medical University
Tashkent city

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18901470>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 02ND March 2026

Accepted: 05th March 2026

Online: 07th March 2026

KEYWORDS

*Study of the significance of MRI
in the differential diagnosis of
cardiac tumors*

ABSTRACT

Heart tumors are rare, but have a high clinical and prognostic risk. [1] Primary heart tumors occur in approximately 0.0011-0.031% of the world's population, i.e., 0.088-2.48 million people out of the current 8 billion population. [2] Malignant tumors are accompanied by myocardial infiltration, multiple chamber lesions, pericardial effusion, and thromboembolism, which poses a high risk of mortality for patients. [3,4] Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) is the most reliable and non-invasive diagnostic tool for assessing cardiac tumors.

Heart tumors are rare, but have a high clinical and prognostic risk. [1] Primary heart tumors occur in approximately 0.0011-0.031% of the world's population, i.e., 0.088-2.48 million people out of the current 8 billion population. [2] Malignant tumors are accompanied by myocardial infiltration, multiple chamber lesions, pericardial effusion, and thromboembolism, which poses a high risk of mortality for patients. [3,4] Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) is the most reliable and non-invasive diagnostic tool for assessing cardiac tumors

Purpose of the study. Study of the significance of MRI in the differential diagnosis of cardiac tumors.

Materials and methods. The study included 73 patients with suspected heart tumors (E:A:55:18, mean age 40±5.8). All patients underwent an ultrasound examination of the heart (ultrasound, echocardiography), followed by an MRI to clarify the diagnosis. MRI examination was performed with T1-weight and T2-weight imaging, cine-MRI, contrast enhanced perfusion, and Magny contrast.

Result. In 73 patients diagnosed with cardiac tumors using ultrasound, 24 (33%) patients had benign tumors, 20 (27%) had malignant tumors, and 21 (28.8%) had thrombi; Among patients diagnosed with heart tumors by MRI, benign tumors were observed in 27 (37%), malignant tumors in 22 (30%), and thrombi in 24 (33%) patients. Malignant tumors were more common in patients with long-term bad habits ($p < 0.002$), shortness of breath and chest pain were observed in patients with a left ventricular thrombus ($p < 0.016$). Malignant tumors were associated with large size, infiltration, pericardial fluid, and signal indistinctness ($p = 0.001$), and in cardiac thrombi, contrast media did not accumulate, a bright signal was reflected ($p = 0.001$). MRI was accurate in 91.2% compared to the results of surgical operations; benign tumor - 91.3%, malignant tumor - 94%, thrombus - 83%. On average, over 2.9 years of

observation, the mortality rate in patients with thrombus and benign tumor was similar ($p=0.678$), while in patients with malignant tumor it was higher ($p=0.035$). Long-term risk of death was associated with the patient's age, tumor localization and size, signal ambiguity, and pericardial fluid ($p<0.01$).

Conclusion. Tumors of the heart are rare, but have a high mortality risk. MRI allows for the precise differentiation of benign, malignant tumors, and thrombi in the heart. MRI gives a result with 91% accuracy. Therefore, MRI is the most reliable tool for diagnosing and predicting heart tumors.

References:

1. Lennerz C, et al. Cardiac tumors: Updated classifications and main clinico-pathological findings. PubMed; 2024
2. Cardiac Tumors: Primary cardiac tumors on the verge of oblivion: a European experience over 15 years. J Cardiothorac Surg.
3. Karigyo CJT, et al. Cardiac Tumor Review. Braz J Cardiovasc Surg
4. Imaging of cardiac masses: an updated overview. J Cardiovasc Echography

